

Childhood Insomnia: A Narrative Review on the Efficacy and Safety of Traditional Chinese Medicine and Naturopathy.

Cátia Relvas¹ ,
and Mafalda Araújo² .

¹ ABS – Health Level, Atlântico Business School, Vila Nova de Gaia, Porto, Portugal;

² COOPMIC - Integrative and Complementary Medicine Cooperative, Lisbon, Portugal.

* Correspondence: susanabatista5@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Sleep is essential for a child's development, but insomnia is a prevalent issue that can be associated with behavioural, medical, neurological, or psychological conditions. While conventional treatments often involve medication and behavioural therapies, there is a growing parental interest in natural, complementary approaches like Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) and Naturopathy.

Methods: This narrative review analyses scientific literature on TCM and Naturopathy for treating childhood insomnia. A bibliographic search was conducted in databases like PubMed, SciELO, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar using a combination of key terms. The review includes studies published from January 2000 to March 2025 in both Portuguese and English, focusing on reviews, clinical trials, and observational and experimental studies. The analysis aims to identify the therapeutic benefits and underlying physiological mechanisms.

Results: *Tui Na* massage seems to improve sleep, behaviour, digestion, and psychomotor development in children, as well as to strengthen the mother-child bond. Moreover, acupuncture shows potential for treating specific symptoms like night crying. Tai Chi and *Qigong*, while not directly studied for sleep, were found to reduce stress and anxiety, which can indirectly benefit sleep quality. Naturopathic herbal medicine using plants like valerian, chamomile, and lemon balm demonstrates promise in treating insomnia, while aromatherapy, with essential oils such as lavender and chamomile, shows clear benefits for sleep quality.

Overall, the quality of evidence was considered moderate due to methodological limitations like small sample sizes, lack of blinding, and study heterogeneity.

Conclusion: Both TCM and Naturopathy offer safe and potentially effective alternatives to pharmacological treatments for childhood insomnia. The reviewed practices, including *Tui Na* massage, acupuncture, herbal medicine, aromatherapy, Tai Chi, and *Qigong*, show favourable results in promoting sleep and overall well-being. However, there is a clear need for more rigorous, large-scale, randomised clinical trials to further validate their efficacy and safety in a paediatric context.

Keywords: Childhood Insomnia; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Naturopathy; *Tui Na* Massage; Acupuncture; Herbal Medicine; *Qigong*.

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1. Background

Sleep is a vital part of physiological, emotional, and neurocognitive development. It is therefore recommended that parents be asked during paediatric consultations if they have any concerns about their child's sleep, if the child snores, or if they wake up feeling rested. These brief questions are efficient and effective measures through which the identification and subsequent treatment of sleep problems can be improved in children ^{1,2}.

Approximately 20% to 30% of infants cry excessively and have sleep difficulties for no apparent reason, causing parental stress ³. In addition to the unfavourable secondary consequences for maternal and family well-being, sleep problems are prevalent and have been associated with obesity, poor behaviour, and low academic performance. However, studies also reveal that paediatricians often fail to diagnose sleep problems and do not pay enough attention to sleep during routine check-ups ⁴.

There are many aspects of sleep that have a major impact on the health and well-being of children and their families. While parents frequently complain about sleep difficulties in infants and young children, paediatricians report receiving little formal training in sleep medicine. Therefore, understanding and diagnosing childhood sleep problems requires a solid grasp of fundamental physiology, the evolution of sleep patterns, normal sleep duration, and the numerous factors that influence them. Additionally, to promote long-term healthy sleep patterns in children and prevent sleep problems, paediatricians must address sleep hygiene and the early adoption of healthy sleep habits ⁴.

In this context, insomnia, a prevalent sleep disorder, frequently emerges. It is characterised by inadequate sleep duration, poor sleep quality, difficulties in initiating or maintaining sleep, and difficulties in resuming sleep after waking. Prolonged insomnia, in turn, deeply impacts individuals' health ^{5,6}.

The study by Cohen *et al.* ⁷ analysed data from the 2012 National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) and concluded that 6.4% of children aged 6 to 17 in the U.S. reported regular sleep difficulties, which amounts to about 1.5 million children. Sleep difficulties were significantly associated with older age, worse health status, more school absences, and comorbidities such as anxiety, migraines, asthma, respiratory allergies, and eczema. Among children with sleep difficulties, 29% used some form of complementary and alternative therapy (supplements like melatonin, manipulation therapies, mind-body techniques, special diets, movement therapies, and practices like acupuncture, homoeopathy, and naturopathy), with non-vitamin and mineral supplements (such as melatonin) being the most common. However, the authors recommend more research on the efficacy and safety of these approaches for treating sleep disorders in children ⁷.

Additionally, due to changing lifestyles and mental health concerns, the prevalence of insomnia is increasing, and conventional treatments for insomnia primarily involve medication and behavioural therapies ⁷⁻⁹. However, the prolonged use of medication is associated with an increased risk of adverse effects ^{10,11}. In this context, TCM demonstrates distinct advantages in the treatment of insomnia.

TCM stands out for its non-invasive interventions. This focus is further justified by the growing parental interest in natural treatment options, as shown by recent epidemiological studies indicating that about 30% of children with sleep difficulties have turned to complementary therapies, including naturopathy and acupuncture ⁷. The growing empirical evidence that supports its efficacy, especially in integrative approaches, defined as therapeutic models that combine conventional medicine with evidence-based complementary methods such as acupuncture, herbal medicine, and *Tui Na* massage, also plays a part ¹². Furthermore, in recent years, TCM clinical guidelines for insomnia have shown substantial progress. For example, a 2024 review by Ye *et al.* ⁵ mapped 13 global guidelines, highlighting high-certainty, evidence-based recommendations for herbal medicine prescriptions, body and auricular acupuncture, demonstrating a transition from expert consensus to recommendations based on robust empirical data.

Naturopathy, in turn, is a distinct system of primary healthcare, being an art, science, philosophy, and practice of diagnosing, treating, and preventing disease. Moreover, naturopathy is distinguished by the principles on which its practice is based, as it uses natural methods to promote physical, mental, and emotional well-being ¹³.

In this context, the study by Pranav *et al.* ¹⁴ found that participants who received naturopathic treatment showed remarkable improvements in sleep quality, a reduction in daytime sleepiness, and a decrease in working memory performance. These findings suggest that the cephalic shower, a non-pharmacological naturopathic intervention based on hydrotherapy, may have the potential to improve cognitive function and sleep quality in

sleep-deprived individuals. This technique consists of applying water at about 41 °C, poured from the back of the neck towards the head, with the patient in a ventral position, for about five minutes at night. The stimulus induces a sedative effect, promoting relaxation and the regulation of the autonomic nervous system, namely through parasympathetic activation.

The observed benefits can be attributed to the dominance of the parasympathetic system, which likely reduces cortisol and acetylcholine levels, thus suppressing the activity of the brain's reticular activating system and decreasing cortical arousal. On the other hand, vagal stimulation can help initiate sleep. However, the study lacks analysis in the paediatric population, so research on these age groups is necessary to confirm the applicability of naturopathy in the treatment of insomnia in children ¹⁴.

With greater prominence in Western countries such as the U.S., Canada, and Australia, where the demand for naturopaths is linked to the search for more organic and comprehensive healthcare approaches, the article by Leach *et al.* ¹⁵ presents naturopathy as one of the complementary medicine techniques used by children and adolescents. The review also included studies that reported the use of naturopathic services to treat common ailments such as colds, sleep disorders, digestive problems, mild anxiety, and to promote general well-being. Parents see the naturopathic practice, which integrates lifestyle guidance, dietary counselling, and the use of natural supplements, as a safer, more personalised, and less invasive alternative to traditional treatments. In addition to highlighting the importance of educating parents and caregivers on the informed use of these treatments, the article suggests that the growing use of naturopathy reflects not only personal preferences but also perceived gaps in traditional biomedical services. This suggests a need for public policies that regulate and integrate these practices into the healthcare system safely and effectively.

1.1. Childhood Sleep

Sleep in early childhood, considered from birth to six years old, is essential for a child's physical, mental, and emotional development. It is also important to note that sleep patterns begin to form in the womb before the baby is born. The foetus exhibits sleep cycles in the third trimester of pregnancy, with phases that resemble REM (rapid eye movement) and non-REM sleep, which suggests an early preparation of the brain for the sleep patterns that develop after birth ¹⁶.

During pregnancy, maternal signals are the sole determinants of the foetus's circadian rhythms. The maternal suprachiasmatic nucleus, which controls the biological clock, adjusts to pregnancy by altering hormone levels, cortisol levels, body temperature, and metabolism. The developing foetus receives signals about the time of day through these changes, and maternal signals are essential for synchronising the foetal suprachiasmatic nucleus and peripheral clocks. Despite the presence of foetal biological clock genes and their rhythmicity *in vitro*, they are not fully functional *in vivo*, which implies that the establishment of circadian rhythms depends on both central and peripheral maturation, as well as maternal signals ¹⁶.

In particular, animal studies, especially in primates, have shown that maternal melatonin crosses the placenta and interacts with foetal receptors, thus playing a crucial role in the development of the foetal circadian rhythm. Thus, changes in maternal melatonin levels, such as those caused by shift work or continuous light, have a detrimental effect on the development of the foetus's circadian rhythm and stress hormone levels, cortisol. In this circumstance, these rhythms can be restored with melatonin supplementation by the pregnant woman ¹⁶.

In the first few months of life, sleep is polyphasic, which means it is distributed over many hours of the day and night, with no clear distinction between day and night. Although the baby sleeps between 14 and 17 hours a day, this sleep is divided into brief naps of different durations, with regular awakenings. Sleep patterns consolidate as the baby develops. From four to eleven months, babies need 12 to 15 hours of sleep, and it is not

uncommon for them to start sleeping for long periods at night. The sleep pattern begins to become more consistent from the first year of life, and the frequency of naps gradually decreases¹⁷.

According to the National Sleep Foundation¹⁷, babies' sleep cycles are shorter than adults', lasting about 50 minutes during the first few months. Each cycle consists of phases of light sleep, deep sleep, and REM sleep, which is the phase in which the most vivid dreams and greatest brain activity occur. REM sleep is the most prevalent sleep phase in newborns and is crucial for brain development, especially for memory consolidation and the growth of neurons^{18,19}. The cycles increasingly resemble those of adults in terms of duration and structure as the months pass, and deep sleep increases¹⁷.

From the perspective of TCM, this alternation between sleep phases can be related to the dynamics of *Yin* and *Yang*, with *Yin* associated with hypofunction, rest, and regeneration, and *Yang* with hyperfunction, activity, and stimulation. Deep sleep (non-REM), characterised by immobility and regeneration, is associated with the predominance of *Yin*, while the REM phase, marked by greater brain activity and rapid eye movement, is seen as an expression of *Yang*. The balance between these two phases reflects the functional balance between *Yin* and *Yang*, which is essential for the child's health and harmonious development.

At older ages, it is important to remember that sleep is still necessary. Between one and two years of age (toddler stage), children should sleep 11 to 14 hours a day. It is recommended to have 10 to 13 hours of sleep for children between three and five years old (preschool age). School age begins at 6, and 9 to 11 hours of sleep are recommended. Established by the National Sleep Foundation¹⁷ are based on comprehensive scientific evaluations and aim to help children maintain a healthy sleep schedule, which is essential for their overall health.

Since growth hormone is released mainly during deep sleep, getting enough sleep at this stage of life has significant consequences for physical development, as well as for the control of the immune and emotional systems^{20,21}. Young children who do not get enough sleep are more prone to irritability, attention and behavioural problems, and a higher likelihood of developing chronic health problems in the future^{17,22,23}.

In short, it is crucial to understand the needs and characteristics of sleep in early childhood to promote healthy and complete development. From the womb to the first years of life, sleep is essential for the child's development and health.

1.2. Childhood Insomnia

Newborns spend about 70% of the first few weeks after birth sleeping, and their sleep episodes are distributed equally over the 24 hours of the day, with no defined rhythm. By about 15 weeks, they have apparently more consolidated episodes of wakefulness and sleep, and between 6 and 9 months of age, most babies can sleep through the night, having at least 6 hours of consolidated sleep episodes. However, along with the development of the circadian system, the maturation of the homeostatic sleep process also contributes to the establishment of the 24-hour pattern observed in the first months of life. In addition, the individual variability in sleep time and duration is great, representing differences in the manifestation of the development of sleep-wake and circadian synchronicity¹⁶.

As a natural physiological condition essential for everyone, sleep has a special influence on children, as it is a period of development and growth. However, children have a wide range of sleep disorders, which are very prevalent²⁴⁻²⁷.

Although children are born physiologically ready to sleep, the total amount of sleep time decreases with age, the REM-NREM (rapid eye movement/non-rapid eye movement) sleep cycle changes, the amount of continuous sleep time increases, and the ability to fall back asleep on their own after regular sleep interruptions develops. As a result, it is crucial to first recognise this variation to provide a better perception and direction on how to

adjust normal sleep patterns. In turn, children's sleep problems can be divided into primary and secondary categories and are thought to result from a link between their biological constitution and their interactions with their parents²⁸.

The International Classification of Sleep Disorders²⁹, published by the American Academy of Sleep Medicine, defines insomnia as an almost daily complaint of insufficient or non-restorative sleep, despite adequate opportunities for sleep²⁹. In turn, children with difficulty sleeping are more prone to a variety of other health problems, such as hyperactivity, and behavioural and social changes⁷.

According to Martins *et al.*³⁰, up to six months of age, the adoption of healthy sleep practices by children shows a positive correlation with maternal knowledge about sleep hygiene. Given these findings, it is recommended that sleep education, which aims to provide parents with methods to promote the development of healthy habits and routines, begin as early as possible, ideally during pregnancy and the early postpartum period. Additional studies are needed to determine the best time and technique to educate parents on this topic, to improve the quality of their children's sleep.

There are two main categories of childhood insomnia: behavioural insomnia and insomnia linked to medical, neurological, or psychological disorders. Inappropriate associations with falling asleep, such as the need for parental presence or inconsistent bedtime regulations, are common causes of behavioural insomnia. Secondary to medical reasons, insomnia is more common in the first year of life and can be linked to problems such as ear infections, allergies, colic, or gastroesophageal reflux. Insomnia can also be linked to conditions such as anxiety, depression, or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), epilepsy, and cognitive deficits as children get older³¹.

According to Garcês²⁸, insomnia in the paediatric population can be classified as primary or secondary. Primary insomnia falls into the category of dyssomnias and results from factors intrinsic to the child's own sleep, which may originate from poor sleep habits, anxiety, or behavioural characteristics. Subtypes include behavioural insomnia of childhood (related to sleep onset or setting limits), psychophysiological, adjustment, paradoxical, or idiopathic insomnia. Secondary insomnia is associated with other medical or psychiatric conditions or external factors, such as respiratory or neurological diseases, allergies, gastroesophageal reflux, acute events (fever, otitis, teething), or even sleep disturbances such as nightmares and night terrors. Thus, in the paediatric context, this distinction between primary and secondary insomnia is essential for an effective clinical evaluation and for defining the most appropriate treatment, which can vary between behavioural, environmental, and, in selected cases, pharmacological interventions.

From the perspective of TCM, childhood insomnia can be interpreted as a manifestation of a disharmony between organs and energetic systems. Common patterns include imbalances that affect the nervous system, such as mental agitation caused by excess internal heat (linked to the Heart), lack of nourishing and restorative substances (associated with the *Yin* of the Kidney and Liver), or poor digestion, which interferes with mental clarity and the proper functioning of the body. These energetic imbalances can manifest as difficulties in falling asleep, restless sleep, or frequent awakenings.

Non-pharmacological treatments have shown promise in the treatment of chronic insomnia, offering a safe alternative to medications, the long-term use of which can result in tolerance and dependence. According to Passos *et al.*³², the main strategies are physical activity, relaxation, sleep hygiene, phototherapy, paradoxical intention, sleep deprivation, stimulus control, and cognitive therapy. Regular physical activity contributes to sleep regulation, as long as it is not performed close to bedtime. Relaxation techniques, such as deep breathing or meditation, help reduce physiological and mental activation, promoting a state conducive to sleep^{33,34}. Sleep hygiene involves adopting healthy habits related to the environment and bedtime, such as avoiding stimulants or screen exposure before bed³⁵⁻³⁷. Phototherapy uses controlled light exposure to reset the circadian rhythm, being particularly useful in cases of sleep disorders originating from the deregulation of the biological clock³⁸⁻⁴⁰. Paradoxical intention seeks to reduce anxiety related to falling asleep by instructing the patient to try to stay awake instead of focusing on falling asleep^{41,42}.

Sleep deprivation, under clinical guidance, aims to increase homeostatic sleep pressure, facilitating its consolidation³². Stimulus control seeks to associate the bedroom and bed exclusively with sleep, avoiding activities that interfere with this association^{43,44}. Finally, cognitive therapy works on dysfunctional thoughts related to sleep, promoting cognitive restructuring that favours the recovery of normal sleep patterns^{45,46}.

According to research, these treatments reduce the time needed to fall asleep, lengthen the overall duration of sleep, and increase sleep efficiency, which contributes to daytime performance³². By integrating many of these methods, combined therapies have been especially beneficial. In addition, these techniques have helped patients live better by reducing or eliminating the use of sleeping pills. Therefore, behavioural and cognitive treatments are considered acceptable and long-lasting approaches to the management of chronic insomnia³².

2. Methodology

This narrative review aimed to gather and analyse the available scientific literature on the application of TCM and Naturopathy in the treatment of childhood insomnia. To this end, a bibliographic search was conducted in the PubMed, SciELO, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar databases. The search strategy used specific Boolean operators to combine the main terms related to the topic. The specific search formula used was: ("Traditional Chinese Medicine" OR "TCM") AND (Naturopathy OR Naturopathic) AND (Insomnia OR "Sleep Disorders") AND (Children OR Pediatric OR Infant).

The search included studies published between January 2000 and March 2025, to ensure both the historical context and the incorporation of the most recent evidence available.

Studies in Portuguese and English were selected, including reviews, clinical trials, observational studies, and experimental studies. The analysis was descriptive and critical, allowing for the identification of the main therapeutic benefits of these approaches for childhood insomnia, as well as the possible physiological mechanisms underlying the TCM and Naturopathy interventions.

The selection of articles took place in two phases: in the first phase, the titles and abstracts were analysed; in the second phase, the full texts of the potentially eligible articles were analysed.

3. TCM and Naturopathy for Childhood Insomnia

3.1. *Tui Na* Massage

All studies on *Tui Na* massage included in this review covered children in early childhood, ranging from birth to six years of age. Regarding the effects of massage on children, improvements were found in sleep patterns, increased tolerance to better stress management techniques, better control over psychobehavioural states, normal muscle tone, lower levels of stress hormones (cortisol, norepinephrine, among others), higher levels of anti-stress hormones (oxytocin and serotonin), and improvements in self-regulation⁴⁷.

According to Barcia *et al.*⁴⁷, massaging babies is a technique to improve the sensation of touch, which allows parents to use touch to increase their children's awareness. On the other hand, massage promotes the induction of calm and deep sleep. Massage is a traditional practice present in various cultures, including Chinese.

The results of the study by Chen *et al.*⁴⁸ indicate that *Tui Na* massage significantly improves the mother-child bond, promotes physical growth (weight and height), reduces the time of crying or agitation, decreases bilirubin levels, improves motor functions and psychomotor development, and effectively controls digestive problems and pain in infants and children under 5 years of age.

The protocols used in *Tui Na* massage vary depending on the child's age and condition, with daily sessions lasting between 10 and 15 minutes being common. As well, according to Chen *et al.*⁴⁸, many studies adopted interventions with 15 minutes of massage per day for periods between 5 and 15 consecutive days, focusing on areas such as the

abdomen, back, and extremities to regulate digestive functions, improve sleep, and reduce agitation.

The study by Chen *et al.*⁴⁹ showed that paediatric *Tui Na* massage administered by parents improved multiple indicators of children's health and performance, although technical challenges remain that justify more training, continuous follow-up, and research integrating qualitative and quantitative data.

3.2. Acupuncture

Acupuncture is believed to have developed in China over thousands of years and refers to the stimulation of specific, precisely defined points located on meridians (or channels) that are along the surface of the body^{12,50}. The stimulation of acupuncture points can be performed through various methods, including the application of heat, pressure, laser, or the insertion of fine needles⁵¹.

According to Adams *et al.*⁵¹, the literature on the safety of paediatric acupuncture is limited to case reports and small studies, or the inclusion of a small number of children in predominantly adult studies. To produce reliable risk estimates in paediatric acupuncture, large-scale prospective paediatric studies are still needed. According to Cheuk *et al.*⁵², in the case of insomnia treatment, acupuncture and other complementary treatments are still widely used, but the study does not analyse paediatric-aged patients.

In turn, night crying is a common problem in which children cry and become agitated at specific intervals or during the night, so medical intervention is often sought for this common sleep disorder in children. However, paediatric acupuncture is one of the non-medicinal therapies for night crying that parents can try⁵³, provided they have proper training.

According to the review by Ang *et al.*⁵³, the most frequently selected acupuncture points for the treatment of night crying were points EM30 (as illustrated in figure 1, an extra point located on the palmar side of the proximal interphalangeal joints of the index, middle, ring, and little fingers) and PC9 (as illustrated in figure 2, on the middle finger, in the centre of the fingertip). The frequency of treatment varied from a single treatment to a daily treatment for 6 days. All studies used paediatric acupuncture until the symptoms of night crying were completely resolved, and the results concluded that the potential role of paediatric acupuncture in the treatment of night crying needs to be investigated further.

Figure 1: Location of point EM30 (*Sifeng*), located on the palmar side of the proximal interphalangeal joints of the index, middle, ring, and little fingers. Source: *Tuina Simo* Massage⁵⁴.

Figure 2: Location of point PC9 (*Zhongchong*), located at the tip of the middle finger, in the centre of the pulp, exactly at the most distal point of the longitudinal midline of the finger, at the junction between the skin of the pulp and the nail. Source: WHO⁵⁵.

3.3. Aromatherapy

It is important to note that part of the studies analysed in this section were conducted on adult populations. Although the evidence on lavender and chamomile suggests sleep-inducing effects, the direct applicability of these results to paediatric populations is, in many cases, extrapolated and should be interpreted with caution.

Aromatherapy, a centuries-old therapeutic practice, uses 100% pure essential oils to restore physical and mental balance. The aromas and particles released stimulate the limbic system and modulate neurotransmitters such as serotonin, promoting relaxation, anxiety reduction, and deeper, more restorative sleep. Evidence^{56,57} suggests therapeutic potential to improve sleep quality, including in paediatrics, although more studies are needed to confirm efficacy.

Essential oils, such as chamomile and lavender, have shown positive effects in promoting sleep and reducing anxiety, positioning themselves as safe and effective alternatives to conventional medications. Their mechanism of action is related to the inhalation of volatile compounds that act on the limbic system, especially through the modulation of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, involved in regulating mood and sleep^{58,59}. This physiological action contributes to relaxation, sleep induction, and improved sleep quality. In addition, essential oils generally have fewer adverse effects and offer greater application flexibility, such as diffusion in the environment, massage, or baths, which reinforces their usefulness and adaptability in clinical contexts, including paediatrics⁵⁷.

Given these results, their therapeutic application stands out as a relevant approach that encourages further investigation and the development of more focused treatments.

Despite the therapeutic benefits associated with aromatherapy, its application in the paediatric population, particularly in infants under six months, requires strict precautions. Essential oils, although of natural origin, contain highly concentrated compounds that can be irritating or toxic, especially for infants with an immature liver system and particularly sensitive skin and respiratory tracts. For this reason, direct application should be avoided, and it is preferable to use indirect methods, such as diffusers in well-ventilated environments and appropriately diluted formulas. Supervision by qualified professionals is essential to ensure safe and appropriate use, respecting the specificities of age, recommended doses, routes of administration, and the appropriate selection of essential oils.

Thus, essential oils play a fundamental role in improving overall health and well-being, with a focus on sleep quality⁵⁷.

3.4. Herbal Medicine

According to the Brazilian Ministry of Health⁶⁰, herbal medicine (a time-honoured practice that uses medicinal plants and their derivatives for therapeutic purposes, whether in the prevention, treatment, or cure of diseases⁶¹⁻⁶⁵) showed good results in relieving insomnia through the use of medicinal plants such as *Valeriana officinalis*, *Melissa officinalis*, and *Matricaria chamomilla*. Valerian was shown to improve sleep quality without causing significant adverse effects, and its continuous use for 15 to 28 days is recommended. Melissa, also known as lemon balm, had an effect similar to anxiolytics, reducing difficulty falling asleep by about 42%. On the other hand, chamomile also showed efficacy in improving insomnia with regular use. These complementary approaches stand out as safe and effective alternatives for the treatment of insomnia in the paediatric population. As for the dosage, it varies according to the plant and age and should be administered under professional supervision⁶⁰.

Additionally, childhood obstructive sleep apnoea is marked by chronic inflammation and obstruction of the upper airways^{66,67}. In turn, the study by Lai *et al.*⁶⁸ showed that integrative therapy with TCM can significantly reduce the apnoea index in children with obstructive sleep apnoea, in addition to providing more stable BMI control compared to Western medicine alone. Thus, the combination of TCM treatments with Western thera-

pies may represent an effective alternative for children with mild obstructive sleep apnoea. It can also help with weight management in overweight or obese children. Formulas with the greatest potential include a combination of *Forsythia* and *Laminaria, magnolia* extract, *Ephedrae Herba*, and *Glycyrrhizae Radix* and *Rhizoma*, although additional studies are needed to clarify their pharmacological mechanisms and clinical efficacy.

3.5. Tai Chi and Qigong

Tai Chi and *Qigong* are ancient Chinese practices, considered meditative movement exercises that integrate regulated breathing, gentle body movements, and mental concentration⁶⁹. Both seek to promote balance in the physical, emotional, and energetic aspects of the mind-body connection. Tai Chi is typically referred to as an internal martial art, while *Qigong* covers a wider range of activities aimed at promoting vital energy ("Qi")⁷⁰⁻⁷². The attention to posture, the precision of movements, and persistent focus are essential for these practices, which are common among adults for their psychological and physical benefits⁷⁰.

The systematic review by Riskowski *et al.*⁷³ analysed 13 investigations on the effects of Tai Chi and *Qigong* in children and adolescents under 18 years of age. Many studies reported advances in psychosocial components associated with better sleep quality, such as a reduction in stress, anxiety, and behavioural problems, although no research specifically analysed the impact on sleep. In addition, benefits for physical health and quality of life were observed, particularly in children with diseases such as asthma, juvenile arthritis, and fibromyalgia. Despite the lack of concrete information about sleep, the findings indicate that Tai Chi and *Qigong* may offer relevant indirect advantages to children's sleep, which warrants further investigation with particular emphasis on this area.

In turn, the article by Dykens *et al.*⁷⁴ presents *Qigong* as one of the practices taught in the mindfulness-based stress reduction program, aimed at mothers of children with developmental disabilities, such as autism. *Qigong* was practised together with deep breathing and meditation techniques, forming a set of strategies focused on mindfulness and the relaxation of the body and mind. These practices aimed to help mothers cope with high levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. The study results showed that the participants who integrated these activities, including *Qigong*, recorded a significant improvement in sleep quality, with a reduction in insomnia symptoms compared to the group that performed positive psychology practices. This data indicates that *Qigong*, as a component of a mindful approach, can positively contribute to improving the sleep and emotional well-being of mothers with demanding care responsibilities.

4. Final Remarks

Among the therapies analysed, acupuncture, herbal medicine, aromatherapy, *Tui Na* massage, Tai Chi, and *Qigong* share the goal of improving sleep quality in a non-invasive way but vary in the robustness of the evidence. Acupuncture and auriculotherapy present results comparable to conventional treatments but are limited by the methodological quality of the trials. Herbal medicine and aromatherapy show promising benefits but lack robust paediatric studies, and are sometimes extrapolated from adult data. Interventions such as *Tui Na*, Tai Chi, and *Qigong* reveal functional and behavioural improvements, but generalisation is limited by small samples and heterogeneous methodologies^{60,75}.

Tui Na massage^{48,49} has shown benefits in sleep, psychomotor development, and the strengthening of family bonds, especially when administered by parents with adequate supervision, accompanying physiological changes consistent with other methods. Acupuncture, although little studied in children, may be useful in certain situations, such as night crying, according to Ang *et al.*⁵³. It can regulate sleep and reduce concerns in childhood without pharmacological side effects, but the lack of paediatric clinical trials limits its adoption.

Aromatherapy stands out for its simplicity and safety, with lavender and chamomile acting on the limbic system, improving sleep and emotional regulation^{56,57}. Herbal medicine presents scientifically based alternatives, such as valerian, chamomile, and lemon balm, favoured by their moderate sedative and safety effects, with studies such as Lai *et al.*⁶⁸ suggesting benefits also in sleep apnoea. Tai Chi and *Qigong*, although without specific paediatric trials, may contribute to sleep by reducing anxiety and stress^{73,74}.

Naturopathy proposes an organic and self-healing approach. Studies with adults¹⁴ indicate improvements in sleep and cortisol reduction, and despite the lack of research with children, the growing parental demand suggests a social shift towards more organic options³⁰.

Common methodological limitations include a moderate risk of bias, the use of subjective outcomes, small samples, a lack of randomisation, and a lack of blinding. The overall evidence is considered moderate, reinforcing the need for multicentre studies with large samples, standardised protocols, and validated measures, as well as direct comparisons between therapies to evaluate the relative efficacy and possible interactions to better substantiate the efficacy and safety of TCM and Naturopathy in the paediatric context in the treatment of sleep.

The comparative analysis of the therapies shows significant differences in the robustness of the evidence and the methodological quality. Acupuncture and *Tui Na* massage have consistent benefits in improving sleep, reducing nocturnal agitation, and emotional regulation, but most trials have small samples and no control group, limiting generalisation. Aromatherapy and herbal medicine, widely used, are based mainly on observational studies on adults, and the results are extrapolated to paediatrics, which requires caution. Tai Chi and *Qigong* have only indirect evidence, focused on emotional regulation, with no paediatric trials to confirm direct effects on insomnia. Methodological disparities, such as heterogeneity in designs, lack of protocol standardisation, and variability in sleep assessment instruments, reinforce the need for multicentre studies with large samples, randomised design, and validated outcome measures, to allow for more rigorous comparisons of efficacy and safety. These aspects highlight the need for future research with greater methodological rigour, namely randomised clinical trials in paediatrics, with representative samples and well-defined control groups. It would also be relevant to carry out comparative studies between different complementary therapies in order to evaluate their relative efficacy and potential synergy in the treatment of childhood insomnia.

With the aim of systematising the information gathered in this review, a summary table of the main therapeutic interventions analysed is presented below. This table includes data on reported clinical efficacy, the level of available scientific evidence, and the safety of its application in the paediatric population, allowing for a comparative and integrated view of the therapeutic options currently used in the treatment of childhood insomnia within the scope of TCM and Naturopathy.

To prepare the summary table, the level of evidence attributed to each intervention was based on the methodological nature of the studies included in this review. Criteria such as the presence of randomised clinical trials, systematic reviews, evidence-based clinical consensus, and observational studies were considered. The classification was based on the data from the articles analysed, such as the studies by Chen *et al.*⁴⁸ for *Tui Na*, Ye *et al.*⁵ for acupuncture and herbal medicine, and the reviews by the Brazilian Ministry of Health⁶⁰ for herbal medicine and aromatherapy. This approach aimed to offer a comparative evaluation of the therapies, respecting the degree of methodological robustness available for each.

Table 1: Summary Table - Complementary Therapies for Childhood Insomnia.

Therapies	Efficacy	Level of Evidence	Safety in Children
Acupuncture	Reduction of night crying episodes and improved sleep	Moderate to high evidence (RCTs)	Safe when applied by qualified professionals.
<i>Tui Na</i>	Improved sleep, reduced irritability, and digestive problems	Moderate evidence (non-randomised studies)	Considered safe, with application of 10-15 min/day under professional supervision.
Herbal Medicine (Valerian, Chamomile, Melissa)	Reduced sleep latency and mild to moderate insomnia	Low to moderate evidence (narrative reviews)	Generally safe with age-adjusted dosage; pay attention to possible interactions.
Aromatherapy (Lavender, Chamomile)	Improved sleep quality and reduced mild insomnia	Limited evidence (based on observational studies)	Not recommended for <6 months; use with dilution and supervision.
Tai Chi / <i>Qigong</i>	Potential benefits in physical and psychological well-being	Limited evidence (studies with heterogeneity)	Generally safe; more suitable for adolescents due to the need for concentration.

5. Conclusion

The practices of Naturopathy, aromatherapy and naturopathic herbal medicine, as well as the practices of TCM, acupuncture, Tai Chi, *Qigong*, *Tui Na* massage, and also herbal medicine, have shown favourable results in promoting children's sleep, emotional well-being, and overall growth, as well as in promoting family bonds and reducing the consumption of sleeping pills.

Although several studies have revealed substantial clinical and behavioural benefits, mainly when used with professional assistance, more scientific research is still needed, especially in children. Thus, prioritising investment in multidisciplinary research, specialised training, and public policies that promote the safe integration of these practices into the healthcare system is crucial.

Finally, it is concluded that the responsible and evidence-based use of complementary treatments can contribute to improving childhood sleep, as well as promoting a more holistic and humanised approach to health, which takes into account the unique characteristics of each child and promotes physical, mental, and emotional balance from the beginning of life.

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